

THE HEIGHT OF CORN HYBRID PLANTS DEPENDING ON THE APPLICATION OF MACRO- AND MICROFERTILIZERS

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The results of studying the influence of macro and micro fertilizers on the formation of plant height corn hybrids in the conditions of the Right Bank Forest-Steppe of Ukraine are given. The experiment during 2020-2021 studied hybrids of corn (Amaros (FAO 230), Bogatyr (FAO 290), KWS 381 (FAO 350), Carifols (FAO 380)), doses of mineral fertilizers (without fertilizers, N₉₀P₆₀K₆₀, N₁₂₀P₉₀K₉₀) and variants with the use of micro fertilizers (without application, seed treatment YaraVita Teprosyn NP + Zn + spraying corn in the phase of 3-5 leaves YaraVita Maize Boost, seed treatment YaraTera Tenso Cocktail + spraying corn in the phase of 3-5 leaves YaraVita Kombiphos.

Methods. The height of corn plants was determined using a measuring ruler from the soil surface to the top of the main stem by measuring 25 corn plants secured with stakes in two non-contiguous replicates in the stage: 11-12 leaf, flowering corn cobs and wax ripeness of grain. Mathematical processing of the obtained research results was carried out using variance and correlation-regression analyses with the use of Excel and Statistica 12.0 software.

The aim of the study was to determine the effect of macro- and microfertilizers on the formation of plant height in corn hybrids in the conditions of the Right-Bank Forest-Steppe of Ukraine.

1. Dynamics of changes in plant height of mid-early corn hybrids depending on the application of macro- and microfertilizers, days

Hybrid	Macrofertilizers	Microfertilizers*	2020			2021			2022		
			11-12 leaves	Flowering corn cobs	Wax ripeness of grain	11-12 leaves	Flowering corn cobs	Wax ripeness of grain	11-12 leaves	Flowering corn cobs	Wax ripeness of grain
Amaros	Without fertilizers (control)	1	134.0	187.0	209.0	142.0	195.0	216.0	140.0	193,0	213,0
		2	136.0	192.0	212.0	144.0	200.0	220.0	142.0	196,0	216,0
		3	136.0	191.0	212.0	144.0	201.0	220.0	142.0	196,0	216,0
	N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	1	139.0	196.0	214.0	147.0	205.0	224.0	144.0	203,0	222,0
		2	141.0	199.0	219.0	149.0	207.0	226.0	147.0	206,0	225,0
		3	142.0	200.0	219.0	148.0	208.0	227.0	147.0	206,0	226,0
	N ₁₂₀ P ₉₀ K ₉₀	1	145.0	203.0	222.0	151.0	211.0	227.0	150.0	208,0	226,0
		2	147.0	205.0	225.0	153.0	213.0	232.0	151.0	211,0	229,0
		3	146.0	205.0	225.0	153.0	214.0	233.0	152.0	212,0	230,0
Bogatyr	Without fertilizers (control)	1	136.0	196.0	212.0	144.0	202.0	219.0	143.0	199,0	218,0
		2	138.0	198.0	215.0	146.0	205.0	224.0	145.0	203,0	223,0
		3	138.0	198.0	215.0	146.0	205.0	225.0	145.0	203,0	222,0
	N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	1	145.0	205.0	221.0	153.0	213.0	230.0	148.0	210,0	227,0
		2	146.0	207.0	225.0	156.0	215.0	234.0	150.0	213,0	232,0
		3	146.0	207.0	225.0	156.0	216.0	235.0	150.0	214,0	233,0

N ₁₂₀ P ₉₀ K ₉₀	1	150.0	209.0	228.0	158.0	216.0	236.0	152.0	214,0	233,0
	2	152.0	212.0	232.0	160.0	220.0	239.0	154.0	217,0	237,0
	3	153.0	212.0	232.0	159.0	221.0	240.0	154.0	218,0	238,0
Least Significant Difference (LSD) for the factor A		1,4	0,8	1.6	3.1	2.7	1.4	3.4	2.6	1.4
Least Significant Difference (LSD) for the factor B		1,8	1,7	2.7	4.0	3.8	2.6	4.3	3.9	2.5
Least Significant Difference (LSD) for the factor AB		0,3	0,2	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1

*Note, here and further in the tables. Without application (control); 2. Seed treatment with YaraVita Teprosyn NP+Zn (5 l/t) + spraying corn in the 3–5 leaf stage with YaraVita Maize Boost (4 l/ha); 3. Seed treatment with YaraTera Tenso Cocktail (0.15 kg/t) + spraying corn in the 3–5 leaf stage with YaraVita Kombiphos (3 l/ha)

2. Dynamics of changes in plant height of mid-season corn hybrids depending on the application of macro- and microfertilizers, days

Hybrid	Macrofertilizers	Microfertilizers	2020			2021			2022		
			11–12 leaves	Flowering corn cobs	Wax ripeness of grain	11–12 leaves	Flowering corn cobs	Wax ripeness of grain	11–12 leaves	Flowering corn cobs	Wax ripeness of grain
KWS 381	Without fertilizers (control)	1	142.0	200.0	216.0	149.0	208.0	226.0	147.0	205,0	224,0
		2	144.0	202.0	220.0	153.0	211.0	229.0	149.0	207,0	227,0
		3	144.0	202.0	220.0	153.0	211.0	229.0	149.0	207,0	227,0
	N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	1	149.0	211.0	226.0	157.0	219.0	235.0	154.0	217,0	232,0
		2	151.0	213.0	230.0	160.0	223.0	239.0	156.0	220,0	236,0
		3	151.0	213.0	230.0	160.0	224.0	240.0	156.0	221,0	237,0
	N ₁₂₀ P ₉₀ K ₉₀	1	153.0	218.0	232.0	163.0	225.0	241.0	160.0	220,0	239,0
		2	155.0	220.0	236.0	165.0	228.0	245.0	162.0	223,0	242,0
		3	155.0	220.0	236.0	165.0	229.0	246.0	162.0	224,0	243,0
Carifols	Without fertilizers (control)	1	146.0	209.0	224.0	153.0	214.0	231.0	151.0	212,0	230,0
		2	148.0	213.0	227.0	155.0	216.0	234.0	153.0	214,0	233,0
		3	148.0	213.0	227.0	155.0	217.0	234.0	153.0	213,0	233,0
	N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	1	151.0	215.0	232.0	159.0	225.0	244.0	158.0	221,0	239,0
		2	152.0	217.0	235.0	161.0	228.0	249.0	160.0	225,0	243,0
		3	152.0	217.0	235.0	161.0	227.0	248.0	160.0	224,0	242,0
	N ₁₂₀ P ₉₀ K ₉₀	1	156.0	220.0	240.0	165.0	231.0	248.0	162.0	224,0	246,0
		2	158.0	223.0	244.0	167.0	235.0	253.0	164.0	226,0	250,0
		3	158.0	223.0	243.0	167.0	234.0	252.0	164.0	226,0	250,0
Least Significant Difference (LSD) for the factor A		1,4	0,8	1.6	3.1	2.7	1.4	3.4	2.6	1.4	
Least Significant		1,8	1,7	2.7	4.0	3.8	2.6	4.3	3.9	2.5	

Difference (LSD) for the factor B									
Least Significant Difference (LSD) for the factor AB	0,3	0,2	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1

It has been established that the highest impact on the height of hybrid plants is exerted by the application of macrofertilizers – 67.7%, while the share of hybrids is 24.6%. It was noted that microfertilizers have an impact of 5.7% (Fig. 1). The interaction of the factors studied is low, within 1.6%. The low impact of other factors (0.4%) can be explained by the high level of corn cultivation technology in the experimental plots.

Fig. 1. The proportion of the influence of the studied factors on the height indicators of corn hybrids in the wax ripeness phase, %

Conclusions. The highest corn plant was observed during the waxy ripeness phase, with medium-maturing hybrids reaching 222.0–249.0 cm and medium-early hybrids reaching 212.7–236.7 cm. The minimum plant height was observed in the Amaros hybrid without the application of macro- and microfertilizers – 212.7 cm, and the maximum height was recorded for the Karifols hybrid when applying N₁₂₀P₉₀K₉₀ and treating the seeds with YaraVita Teprosyn NP+Zn (5 l/t) and spraying the corn in the 3–5 leaf stage with YaraVita Maize Boost (4 l/ha) – 249.0 cm. The increase in plant height when using macrofertilizers was 3.4–7.6%, and microfertilizers – 1.5–1.8%, compared to areas without their application.